

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

IMPACT OF SMARTPHONES ON EYE HEALTH AMONG HEALTH SCIENCES STUDENTS IN TAIBAH UNIVERSITY, SAUDI ARABIA**Majed Talea Alharbi¹, Ali Ahmed Alem², Hassan Abdullah Alrizqi², Khalid Abdullah Abualnassr², Fahad Abdullah Abualnassr², Amna Mohammed Alshenqeti², Roaa Atallah Alsumiri², Waseem Abdulaziz Alam³.**¹Consultant and Assistant professor, Ophthalmology Department, Taibah University, Almadinah Almunawwarah, KSA., ²College of Medicine, Taibah University, Almadinah Almunawwarah, KSA.,³Consultant and Assistant professor, Ophthalmology Department, Taibah University, Almadinah Almunawwarah, KSA.**Abstract:**

Background: Smartphones using is growing up worldwide, they were used by 1.85 billion people in 2014 and expected to be 2.87 billion in 2020. Just over 36% of the world's population is projected to use a smartphone by 2018, up from about 10% in 2011. Saudi Arabia specifically has more than 44 million mobile phone subscribers and 88% rate of smartphone ownership, which is almost double the international average.

Aim: This study aims to determine the impact of smartphones on eye health among health sciences students in Taibah University.

Method: This is a cross-sectional study conducted on health science students at Taibah University in AL-Medina Saudi Arabia during 2019. The data analysis performed by using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences [SPSS] version 21. Patient characteristics were conducted using descriptive statistics where numbers and percentages and mean \pm standard deviation were used to presents all study results.

Results: There were 650 participants who were recruited in this study. Age range was from 17 to 56 years old, mean 21.8 [SD 2.4]. Females were dominant against males [61.8% vs 38.2%] where most of them were medical students [65.1%]. Many participants spend long duration of Smartphone used per day [>3 hours] with 78.0% and nearly all participants were using smartphone before bed [97.7%] while 72.7% used smartphone 30 minutes or more before going to sleep. Using smartphone before bed and painful or sore eyes were identified as the significant factors of prolong used of smartphone that affected eyes health.

Conclusion: In this study, 4 out 5 students have used smartphone more than three hours per day. This clearly indicates that smartphone conquers a greater part of everyday life. We also revealed that using smart phone before bed and pain or sore eyes as the significant factors of prolong used of smartphone that affects eyes health.

Keywords: Smartphone, mobile phone, eyes, health science students, vision.

Corresponding author:**Majed Talea Alharbi,**Consultant and Assistant professor, Ophthalmology Department,
Taibah University, Almadinah Almunawwarah, KSA.Mobile No:0506304077, Email: mt-alharbi@hotmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Majed Talea Alharbi et al., *Impact Of Smartphones On Eye Health Among Health Sciences Students In Taibah University, Saudi Arabia., Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2019; 06[02].

INTRODUCTION:

The smartphone combines the services of the Internet and a mobile phone. Smartphones offer qualitatively different services in addition to the benefits that the Internet offers. Young people watch videos, express themselves, communicate with friends, and search for information using smartphones, while older people use their smartphone for having video calls with their children living far away and for playing games. The portability and accessibility of a smartphone make it possible to use it anywhere, for any duration.

Smartphones using is growing up worldwide, they were used by 1.85 billion people in 2014 and expected to be 2.87 billion in 2020. Just over 36% of the world's population is projected to use a smartphone by 2018, up from about 10% in 2011.[1] Saudi Arabia specifically has more than 44 million mobile phone subscribers and 88% rate of smartphone ownership, which is almost double the international average.[2]

China, the most populous country in the world, leads the smartphone industry. The number of smartphone users in China is forecast to grow from around 563 million in 2016 to almost 675 million in 2019. Around half of the Chinese population is projected to use a smartphone by 2020. The United States is also an important market for the smartphone industry, with around 223 million smartphone users in 2017. By 2019, the number of smartphone users in the U.S. is expected to increase to 247.5 million[3] .

Smartphones differ from ordinary mobile phones in the manner of use. While the main purpose of mobile phones has been for calling and talking on the phone, smartphones involve more interactions in which the eye is involved, such as sending text messages, watching video clips and playing games. Therefore, the time users spend consistently staring at the screen is longer with smartphones than with ordinary mobile phones. It has been speculated that the increase in smartphone use could have adverse effects on ocular health[4] .

Smartphones offer several conveniences in our life, but we also need to be aware of the negative effects of smartphone use.[3] Smartphones negative effects mainly in the eye health includes : dry eye, blurring of vision, lacrimation, redness and visual disturbance.

Dry-eye disease is a condition that occurs when the eyes don't produce enough tears, which results in eyes becoming red, swollen and irritated usually associated with older people, specialists believe it is underdiagnosed in children. When we stare at screens,

we blink less which means our tear film evaporates faster and our risk of dry-eye disease increases[5] .

Computer Vision Syndrome [CVS], or Digital Eye Strain [DES], describes a group of eye and vision-related problems that result from prolonged smart devices use. The most common symptoms associated with [CVS] are eyestrain, headaches, blurred vision, dry eyes and neck and shoulder pain. These symptoms may be caused by poor lighting, glare on a digital screen, improper viewing distances, poor seating posture, uncorrected vision problems.[3] The extent to which individuals experience visual symptoms often depends on many factors including the level of their visual abilities and the amount of time spent looking at a digital screen. Uncorrected vision problems like farsightedness and astigmatism, inadequate eye focusing or eye coordination abilities, aging changes of the eyes, such as presbyopia can all contribute to the development of visual symptoms when using a computer or digital screen device.[3] Hazardous effects of blue light range in smart devices has been recently considered a significant risk factor of ocular problem which can damage both the cornea and the retina by inducing phototoxicity and oxidative stress.[4]

Many of the visual symptoms experienced by users are only temporary and will decline after stopping computer work or use of the digital device.[4] However, the long-term visual effects of intense and chronic smart mobile device use have not been extensively investigated.[5] Many studies show that the side effect of its use among Saudi population are headaches [21.6%], sleep disturbances [4.%], tension [3.9%], fatigue [3%], and dizziness [2.4%].[6] Another study done in Saudi Arabian found that 44.4% of the medical student developed headaches, decreased concentration, memory loss, hearing loss, and fatigue to the use of their mobile phones.[6] This study aims to the determine the impact of smartphones on eye health among health sciences students in Taibah University.

METHODOLOGY:

This is a cross-sectional study conducted on health science students at Taibah University in AL-Medina Saudi Arabia during 2019. We randomly collected 500 responses from health science students at Taibah University in Medina. All health science students at Taibah University in medina city were **included** in this study. Students from other facilities and other universities were **excluded** from the study. A structural questionnaire was used to record eye problems in the past month and its relation with

smartphone use. It distributed among health sciences students in Taibah University to determine the impact of smartphone on eye health. The ocular symptoms were selected regarding to previous studies are blurred vision, redness, visual disturbance, secretions, lacrimation and dryness. We determined the percent of each symptom and detected the most common symptoms associated with smartphone use.

In the questionnaire We determined **the sociodemographic data** in form of age and gender. **University related data** as the faculty and academic year. **Smartphone use data** in form of number of hours daily, using of smartphone before going to bed or sleeping. **Eye problems data** as sensitivity to light, feeling of dust, pain, blurred vision, decreased visual acuity. **The effect of eye problems on usual daily functions** as reading, driving at night, working with computer or ATM and watching TV. **Eye conditioning wit different situations** like windy weather, low humidity and trauma. **Assessment Vision** by determining if they wear glasses or contact lenses and if they did any Ocular surgery before.

The data analysis performed by using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences [SPSS] version 21. Patient characteristics were conducted using descriptive statistics where numbers and percentages and mean \pm standard deviation were used to presents all study results. Inferential statistics had also been conducted where frequencies and proportions were used to compare dependent variable versus independent variables. A p-value cut off point of 0.05 at 95% CI used to determine statistical significance.

The analyses measure the relationship between dependent variable and independent variables by using chi square test. Binary logistics regression has been conducted as well to predict the likelihood effect of outcome variable and independent factors where odds ratio and confidence interval had also been reported.

In the inferential analysis, independent variables had been recoded into binary to match with the binary logistics regression. Characteristics of effect of smartphone used in eyes health had been recoded into the following classification such as; categories such as; "None" has been recoded into "No" coded as 2 while "Some of the time", "Half of the time", "Most of the time" and "All the time" has been recoded into "yes" coded as 1.

RESULTS:

There were 650 participants who were recruited in this study. Age range was from 17 to 56 years old, mean 21.8 [SD 2.4]. Females were dominant against males [61.8% vs 38.2%] where most medical students [65.1%]. Fifth level students were slight higher [22.6%], followed by second level [20.2%] and third year level [19.3%] while the least participants were first year level [9.6%]. Many participants spends long duration of Smartphone used per day [>3 hours] with 78.0% and nearly all participants were using smartphone before [97.7%] while 72.7% used smartphone 30 minutes or more before going to sleep [Table 1].

Table 1: Socio demographic characteristics of students

Study variables	N [%] [n=650]
Age in years [mean \pm SD]	21.8 \pm 02.4
Gender	
• Male	231 [38.2%]
• Female	374 [61.8%]
College	
• Medicine	394 [65.1%]
• Nursing	67 [11.1%]
• Pharmacy	67 [11.1%]
• Laboratory	33 [05.5%]
• Dentistry	18 [03.0%]
• Physiotherapy	15 [02.5%]
• Radiology	07 [01.2%]
• Respiratory	04 [0.7%]
Academic Year	

• First Level	58 [09.6%]
• Second level	122 [20.2%]
• Third level	117 [19.3%]
• Fourth level	83 [13.7%]
• Fifth level	137 [22.6%]
• Sixth level	88 [14.5%]
Duration of Smartphone used per day	
• ≤3 hours	133 [22.0%]
• >3 hours	472 [78.0%]
Using Smartphone before bed	
• Yes	591 [97.7%]
• No	14 [02.3%]
Duration of Smartphone used before sleep	
• <30 minutes	165 [27.3%]
• ≥30 minutes	440 [72.7%]

Figure 1 presented the characteristics of eyes toward different situation. Based on the results, most of the students were having excellent eye interaction. This was based on the 12 questions about the characteristics of eyes when encountering some instances such as eyes that are sensitive to light, eyes that feel gritty, painful or sore eyes blurred vision, poor vision, reading, driving at night, working with a computer or bank machine [ATM], watching TV,

windy conditions, places or areas with low humidity and areas that are air conditioned. Many of them stated that they were not affected with those situations with relatively small group were affected all the time. There were 44.8% of the students who were wearing eyes glasses whereas 25.5% preferred contact lens. Only 12.6% had history of eye trauma and 7.9% were having history of ocular surgery [Figure 2].

Figure 1: Characteristics of eyes toward different situation

Figure 2: Student practices in relation to eyes health

We conducted chi square test at **table 2** to measure the relationship between the duration of smartphone used per day among socio demographic and characteristics of eyes toward different instances. It was revealed that using smartphone before bed [$X^2 = 10.300$, $p=0.001$] and painful or sore eyes [$X^2=5.804$,

$p=0.016$] were both shows significant relationship to prolong used of smartphone. However, we could not significant relationship on age group in years, gender, college, academic year, eyes that are sensitive to light, eyes that feel gritty, blurred vision and poor vision.

Table 2: Relationship between duration of smartphone used per day among socio demographic and characteristics of eyes toward different situations

Characteristics	>3 hours N [%] [n=472]	≤3 hours N [%] [n=133]	P-value §
Age group in years			
• ≤20 years	158 [33.5%]	41 [30.8%]	0.566
• >20 years	314 [66.5%]	92 [69.2%]	
Gender			
• Male	172 [36.4%]	59 [44.4%]	0.097
• Female	300 [63.6%]	74 [55.6%]	
College			
• Medicine	306 [64.8%]	88 [66.2%]	0.775
• Non-medicine	166 [35.2%]	45 [33.8%]	
Academic Year			
• Junior Level ^a	235 [49.8%]	62 [46.6%]	0.518
• Senior Level ^b	237 [50.2%]	71 [53.4%]	
Using Smartphone before bed			
• Yes	466 [98.7%]	125 [94.0%]	0.001 **

• No	06 [01.3%]	08 [06.0%]	
Eyes that are sensitive to light			
• Yes	328 [69.5%]	85 [63.9%]	0.222
• No	144 [30.5%]	48 [36.1%]	
Eyes that feel gritty			
• Yes	260 [55.1%]	82 [61.7%]	0.177
• No	212 [44.9%]	51 [38.3%]	
Painful or sore eyes			
• Yes	251 [53.2%]	55 [41.4%]	0.016 **
• No	221 [46.8%]	78 [58.6%]	
Blurred Vision			
• Yes	217 [46.0%]	61 [45.9%]	0.982
• No	255 [54.0%]	72 [54.1%]	
Poor vision			
• Yes	270 [57.2%]	76 [57.1%]	0.990
• No	202 [42.8%]	57 [42.9%]	

^aFirst level to third level.

^bFourth level to sixth level.

[§]P-value has been calculated using chi square test.

******Significant at ≤ 0.05 level.

Binary regression analysis has been conducted at **table 3** to ascertain the effect of prolong used of smartphone from the socio demographic and characteristics of eyes toward different instances. Regression analysis included in the model such as; age group in years, gender, college, academic year, using smartphone before bed, eyes that are sensitive

to light eyes that feel gritty, painful or sore eyes, blurred vision and poor vision. Analysis revealed that, using smartphone before bed [odds ratio = 0.201, p-0.004] and pain or sore eyes [odds ratio = 0.996, p-0.016] were both shows significant effect on prolong used of smartphone. Other variables included in the model shows no significant effect.

Table 3: Regression analysis to predict the influence of prolong used of smartphone [>3 hours] per day among socio demographic and characteristics of eyes toward different situation

Characteristics	Odds ratio	95% CI	P-value
Age group in years			
• ≤ 20 years	Ref		
• >20 years	0.886	0.585 – 1.341	0.566
Gender			
• Male	Ref		
• Female	1.391	0.941 – 2.054	0.098
College			
• Medicine	Ref		
• Non-medicine	1.061	0.707 – 1.592	0.775
Academic Year			
• Junior Level ^a	Ref		
• Senior Level ^b	0.881	0.599 – 1.295	0.518

Using Smartphone before bed			
• Yes	Ref		
• No	0.201	0.069 – 0.590	0.004 **
Eyes that are sensitive to light			
• Yes	Ref		
• No	0.777	0.519 – 1.165	0.223
Eyes that feel gritty			
• Yes	Ref		
• No	1.311	0.884 – 1.944	0.178
Painful or sore eyes			
• Yes	Ref		
• No	0.621	0.421 – 0.917	0.016 **
Blurred Vision			
• Yes	Ref		
• No	0.996	0.677 – 1.465	0.982
Poor vision			
• Yes	Ref		
• No	0.998	0.676 – 1.472	0.990

CI – Confidence Interval.

^aFirst level to third level.

^bFourth level to sixth level.

**Significant at ≤ 0.05 level.

DISCUSSION:

Majority of the students in this study uses smartphone more than 3 hours per day [78.0%]. This result is comparable from the study published by Hegazy et al. [7] The study was about “Mobile Phone Use and Risk of Adverse Health Impacts among Medical Students in Jeddah.” They reported that among 472 students they surveyed the median hours of smartphone used was more than 5 hours per day [330 min/day]. Our report is also consistent from the study published in India. [8][9] Sadagopan and colleagues assessed the prevalence of smart phone users at risk for developing cell phone vision syndrome among college students. [8] They found out that 80% of the students were using smartphone for about 2 hours per day. On the other hand, Rai and associates published an article entitled “A cross sectional study to assess the effects of excessive use of smartphones among professional college going students.” [9] They revealed that 40% of the college students spent about 4 hours per day on using smartphone. This clearly indicates that smartphone are having high impact on the daily lives of students regardless of its side effects.

Using smartphone before bed and painful or sore eyes are the significant factors of prolong used of

smart phone that affects eyes health being identified in this study. However, we found no association on gender, age group in years, college, academic year and other eyes related characteristics. In Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, Hegazy et al reported that, gender, sleep disturbances, headache, fatigue, depression, nervousness, musculoskeletal pain and visual problems were the significant factors of heavy mobile used. [7] In Iraq, Abed and colleagues stated that, vision problem and sleep disorder were the significant factors of mobile phone addiction [10] while in India, Sadagopan et al reported that eye strain had been the significant factor of smartphone used for Developing Cell Phone Vision Syndrome whereas Rai and associates accounted sedentary, dry eyes, headache and feeling disturbances in sleep as the independent factors of excessive used of smartphone to affect health condition. [8] [9] In Malaysia, Fung et al exhibited in their paper that sleep disturbance, brightness of screen, hours spend per day and usage in dark were having significant relationship in smartphone usage that effect on neurological symptoms while there was no relationship found between dry eyes and prolonged usage of smartphone. [11] Although there are distinctions in the reported significant factors however, the most common side effect of excessive

used of smartphone being reported was about vision problem. Though in this study, blurred vision and poor vision were negatively associated with prolonged use of smartphone nonetheless, we found significance value on pain or sore eyes. In general, the findings of this study are subjected for further validation due to inconsistencies of the study data. Thus, replication of this study subject are highly encourage in a more comprehensive form to obtain better insights regarding the effect of excessive use of smartphone in eyes health.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, 4 out of 5 students have used smartphone more than three hours per day. This clearly indicates that smartphone conquers a greater part of everyday life. We also revealed that using smartphone before bed and pain or sore eyes as the significant factors of prolonged use of smartphone that affects eyes health. As the smartphone becomes the mainstream of digital technology, responsible usage is necessary. Use of smartphone would be beneficial if it is being used in a certain limit to avoid unnecessary effects in health, most especially in eyes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The research team would like to acknowledge the following medical students for their unconditional support and contributions during the process such as ; Najwa Hajraf Alsaadi, Jebreel Mohammed Fallatah, Sawsan Khader Sayed, Mohammed Salem Alhejaili, Ali Majed Almuzaini, Reem Emad Kordi, Nouf Khalid Hammad, Talal Abdullah Mashhor, Abdullah Saeed Alsaedi, Abdullah Tayeb Abdulkareem, Abdulmannan Ahmad Alem and Noura Abdulrahman Omar, Amal Hasabullah Fatani and Ruba Mohammed Saeed.

REFERENCES:

1. Statista [2017] Number of smartphone users worldwide from 2014 to 2020. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/330695/number-of-smartphone-users-worldwide/>
2. Saudi Smartphone Penetration Exceeds Global Average.” 2017. December 20, 2017. <https://www.tahawultech.com/news/saudi-smartphone-penetration-exceeds-global-average/>.
3. Statista[2018]: Number of smartphone users worldwide from 2014 to 2020. Retrieved <https://www.statista.com/statistics/330695/number-of-smartphone-users-worldwide>
4. KISA ISIS [Korea Internet Security Agency Internet Statistics Information System]. Investigation on the smartphone use of 2012 [Korean, translated by author]. Accessed July 30, 2014 from: <http://isis.kisa.or.kr/>
5. Independent[2018]: Dry eye diseases. Retrieved <https://www.independent.co.uk/life-style/health-and-families/smartphone-use-using-risk-of-dry-eye-disease-mobile-phone-social-media-facebook-optical-health-a7513051.html>
6. Computer Vision Syndrome. Available at: <https://www.aoa.org/patients-and-public/caring-for-your-vision/protecting-your-vision/computer-vision-syndrome>. [Accessed: 27th August 2018]
7. Kim, D. J., Lim, C.-Y., Gu, N. & Park, C. Y. Visual Fatigue Induced by Viewing a Tablet Computer with a High-resolution Display. *Korean J Ophthalmol* 31, 388–393 [2017].
8. Al-Khlaiwi T, Meo SA. Association of mobile phone radiation with fatigue, headache, dizziness, tension and sleep disturbance in Saudi population. *Saudi Med J*. 2004;25:732–736
9. Khan MM. Adverse effects of excessive mobile phone use. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health*. 2008;21:289–293.
10. Hegazy AA, Alkhail BA, Awadalla NJ, Qadi M, Al-Ahmadi J. Mobile Phone Use and Risk of Adverse Health Impacts among Medical Students in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *BJMMR*. 2016; 15[1]: 1-11.
11. Sadagopan AP, Manivel R, Marimuthu A, Nagaraj H, Ratnam K, Taherakumar, Selvarajan L, Jeyaraj G. Prevalence of Smart Phone Users at Risk for Developing Cell Phone Vision Syndrome among College Students. *J Psychol Psychother*. 2017; 7:3.
12. Rai S, Saroshe S, Khatri AK, Sirohi S, Dixit S. A cross sectional study to assess the effects of excessive use of smartphones among professional college going students. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2016;3[3]:758-763.
13. Abed NS, Abd RK, Salim ID, Jamal NAR. Health problems of Mobile Phone Addiction for Sample of students and their health awareness at institute technical of kut. *J. Pharm. Sci. & Res*. 2018; 10[2]:412-415.
14. Fung SZ, Ramish Ta/p, Suresh Ma/p, Abhayagunawardhana AN, Ning LK. A Cross Sectional Study on the Effects of Smartphone Usage on Neurological Symptoms Among Undergraduate Students of Melaka-Manipal Medical College. *Public Health and Preventive Medicine*. 2018; 4[3]: 60-7